

MATERIALS FOR LIGHTWEIGHT RADIATION SHIELD FOR CANADIAN POLAR COMMUNICATIONS AND WEATHER (PCW) SATELLITE MISSION

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Abstract

In order to provide satellite coverage to Canadian Arctic, the Canadian Space Agency (CSA) has proposed a Polar Communication and Weather (PCW) satellite mission. The feasibility study for this mission has shown two satellites system in Highly Elliptical Orbits (HEOs) would meet the mission requirements. Unfortunately, HEO is an orbit with harsh radiation environment. Satellite's sensitive microelectronics must be protected using radiation shield. This study is focused on evaluating the radiation shielding effectiveness of polymer composites over traditionally used aluminum. The thickness and dispersion of the reinforcement and the resin layers of the composite have been found to significantly impact its shielding effectiveness

1 Introduction

The Canadian Space Agency (CSA), in conjunction with other government and industrial partners, has carried out a feasibility study for Polar Communications and Weather (PCW) satellite mission to provide essential communications and meteorological services to the Canadian Arctic in response to a long-recognized, but thus far unfulfilled, need. This mission plans to achieve continuous coverage of Canadian northern region with two satellite constellation system in Highly Elliptical Orbit (HEO). Owing to high eccentricity of the orbit, HEO is most preferred for high latitudes region. Previous orbital analysis [1] has shown that above 60°N latitude, geosynchronous satellites provide less coverage of polar region while a constellation of several polar LEO satellites are not efficient for coverage of this region. Since radiation is strongly dependent on altitude and latitude, the

trajectory of HEO makes a satellite in this orbit to interact with various regimes of radiation environment.

CSA has identified three potential HEOs for this mission, namely Molniya, Modified Tundra and Triple Apogee (TAP). While a Molniya orbit would provide an excellent imagery (due to its relatively low apogee altitude) and coverage of Canada's Arctic regions, it also subjects the spacecraft bus and payload to high-concentrations of energetic trapped protons and electrons in the Van Allen Radiation Belts. As such, recent publications [2, 3] in this area have favoured the TAP, citing a compromise between the superior imaging conditions of a Molniya orbit with the spacecraft longevity (associated with a lower radiation dose similar to a geo-synchronous (GEO) of the Modified Tundra orbit). Shielding for space microelectronics is expected to provide an acceptable dose limit with minimum shield mass [4, 5]. Hence, mass of shield required in these orbits poses a challenge for missions in these orbits.

Traditionally, aluminum has been used for radiation protection. Depending on the mission altitude, inclination and the dose rating of the electronics, the thickness of aluminum necessary for shielding can substantially exceed that required for structural strength, resulting in significant weight penalties. Also, highly energetic radiation, such as those experienced in HEO, can also knock protons and neutrons out of the aluminum atoms' nuclei, resulting in to disruption of the operation of the electronic systems [6]. Hence, the aluminum shields for HEOs are likely to be heavier than those used in LEOs and GEOs. Hence, this study is focused on

evaluating the suitability of composite materials with higher specific properties than Al for HEOs

2 Simulation Details

The intense radiation environment in HEOs is mainly due to Van Allen radiation belts (both proton and electron belts). In addition, solar particles and cosmic rays contribute to the total ionization dose (TID) accumulated by a material during the mission. These radiation environments were modeled using standardized models in European Space Agency (ESA) Space ENVironment Information System (SPENVIS) software [7, 8]. ‘Worst case’ radiation environments were modeled and the mission life was for fifteen years.

The resulting fluencies serve as input for the calculation of TID using particle transport simulation code, ESA’s MULASSIS (Multilayered Shielding Simulation Software Tool – Monte Carlo based Geant4 code). A planar shielding geometry was defined and the TID deposited on a silicon detector behind the shield was determined. This TID for various materials are compared to evaluate their shielding efficiency.

A recent study has shown that an improvement in radiation shielding effectiveness as well as reduction in shield weight can be achieved with replacement of the aluminum with polymer composites (low Z materials) in LEO and interplanetary missions [9,10 11]. Therefore, as a first step in designing and developing composites for the identified mission, the radiation shielding effectiveness of a select class of materials was evaluated and compared with aluminum. These include polymeric material such as polyethylene and epoxy and metals such as aluminum, tantalum and tungsten. Since

3 Results and Discussion

Fig.2 shows representative results for predicted TID for aluminum in the three identified orbits. The TID varies inversely with the areal density of the shield (areal density divided by density yields shield

thickness). Similar results were generated for other materials. Since the dose varies with areal density, relative ranking of the weight of shield would depend on the TID chosen for comparison. Hence the areal density required to achieve an arbitrary dose of 50 krad was extracted from these results and compared in Table 1 for different materials.

Among the 5 materials studied, Ta would result in the lightest shield (0.49 g/cm^2) if used in Modified Tundra Orbit. The next material to offer the lightest shield is W (0.68 g/cm^2) in TAP orbit. Slightly behind is PE that offers the lightest shield (0.7 g/cm^2) in Molniya orbit. PE shields are lighter than Al shields in all three HEOs.

Thus, Molniya orbit would satisfy both the mission and the shield weight requirements provided PE is used. Hence, the effect of introducing graphite fibers into PE, on its shielding effectiveness was studied. Five different lay-up configurations were studied.

The first configuration is a two layer configuration of Gr/PE or PE/Gr with each layer having the same areal density of density 0.4 g/cm^2 . The TID results tabulated in Table 2 show that only PE/Gr would have a $\text{TID} \leq 50 \text{ krad}$.

Since composites have to be symmetric, effect of dispersion of the material on TID was studied. In configuration two, the PE and Gr layers of configuration 1 was divided into 4 layers each with the same areal density of 0.1 g/cm^2 . This means, the thickness of one layer of PE would be different from the thickness of one layer of Gr. These eight layers were interdispersed in 4 different ways as shown in Table 3. It can be inferred that only one lay-up would have a $\text{TID} \leq 50 \text{ krad}$. Moreover, the TID recorded for this lay-up is more than the TID recorded for PE/Gr in Table 2 despite having the same total shield thickness.

In configuration 3, the PE and Gr layers of configuration 1 were divided into four layers each. However, the thicknesses of all layers were kept constant unlike configuration 2. Hence, the areal density of each PE and Gr layer was different as shown in Table 4. For this configuration, three lay-ups would have a $\text{TID} \leq 50 \text{ krad}$, despite having the

same total thickness as those of configurations 2 and 3.

In configuration 4, the PE and Gr layers of configuration 1 were divided into eight layers each with same areal density. However, the thickness each layer of PE and Gr were different as shown in Table 5. This is similar to configuration 2; but, the areal density of each layer is half of that in configuration 2. For this configuration, only one lay-up would have a TID ≤ 50 krad, despite having the same total thickness as those of configurations 2, 3, and 4. It can also be observed that the TID if this lay-up is more than that of the lay-up of configuration 2.

In configuration 5, PE and Gr were divided into eight layers similar to configuration 4. However, the PE and Gr layers had the same thickness. The areal density of PE and Gr were different as shown in Table 5. Three lay-ups had TID ≤ 50 krad as against one in configuration 4. Also, one lay-up of this configuration yielded the lowest TID despite having the same total thickness as other configurations.

These results clearly demonstrate the effect of dispersion and thickness of layers on the TID of a composite shielding. This needs to be taken into account while designing a composite shield to meet the radiation requirements.

4 Conclusions

Radiation shielding efficiency of polymer composites was studied through simulation. The thickness and dispersion of the reinforcement and polymer matrix layers have been found to significantly influence the shielding efficiency of polymer composites.

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Fig. 2: TID absorbed by the Si-detector as a function of areal density of Aluminum shield in the 3 orbits

Table 1: Required areal density to meet a TID of 50 Krad for five materials in 3 HEO orbits

Orbit	Shield Thickness (g/cm ²)				
	Al	PE	Ta	W	Epoxy
Molniya	0.90	0.70	1.30	1.22	0.94
Modified Tundra	0.62	0.6	0.49	0.52	0.65
TAP	1.10	0.98	0.76	0.68	1.02

Table 2: TID for PE/Gr shield configuration 1 in Molniya orbit for total areal density of 0.8 g/cm²

Composition and Configuration	Outer layer (g/cm ²)	Inner layer g/cm ²)	TID (Rad)
Gr/PE	0.4	0.4	6.53E+04
PE/Gr	0.4	0.4	4.09E+04

Table 3: TID for PE/ Graphite shield configuration 2 in Molniya orbit for a total areal density of 0.8 g/cm²

Composition and Configuration	PE Lamina AD(g/cm ²) /Th(mm)	Gr Lamina AD(g/cm ²) /Th(mm)	Total Dose in- Si (Rad)
Gr/Gr/PE/PE/PE/PE/Gr/Gr	0.1/1.031	0.1/0.588	5.57E+04
PE/PE/Gr/Gr/Gr/Gr/PE/PE	0.1/1.031	0.1/0.588	5.12E+04
Gr/PE/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/PE/Gr	0.1/1.031	0.1/0.588	6.11E+04
PE/Gr/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/Gr/PE	0.1/1.031	0.1/0.588	4.28E+04

Table 4: TID for PE/ Graphite configuration 3 in Molniya orbit for a constant total thickness of 6.608mm

Composition and Configuration	PE Lamina AD(g/cm ²) /Th(mm)	Gr Lamina AD(g/cm ²) /Th(mm)	Total Dose in- Si (Rad)
Gr/Gr/PE/PE/PE/PE/Gr/Gr	0.078/0.826	0.140/0.826	3.76E+04
PE/PE/Gr/Gr/Gr/Gr/PE/PE	0.078/ 0.826	0.140/0.826	3.69E+04
Gr/PE/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/PE/Gr	0.078/0.826	0.140/0.826	4.59E+04
PE/Gr/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/Gr/PE	0.078/0.826	0.140/0.826	7.31E+04

Table 5: TID PE/ Graphite configuration 4 in Molniya orbit for a total areal density of 0.8 g/cm²

Composition and Configuration	PE Lamina AD (g/cm ²) / Th (mm)	Gr Lamina AD (g/cm ²) /Th(mm)	Total Dose in- Si (Rad)
Gr/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/PE/PE/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/Gr	0.05/0.053	0.05/0.029	7.62E+04
PE/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/Gr/Gr/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/PE	0.05/0.053	0.05/0.029	6.81E+04
Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr	0.05/0.053	0.05/0.029	5.64E+04
PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/GR/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/GR/PE/GR/PE	0.05/0.053	0.05/0.029	4.66E+04

Table 6: TID for PE/ Graphite configuration 5 in Molniya orbit for a constant total thickness of 6.608mm

Composition and Configuration	PE Lamina AD (g/cm²) / Th (mm)	Gr Lamina AD (g/cm²) /Th(mm)	Total Dose in- Si (Rad)
Gr/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/PE/PE/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/PE/ Gr/Gr	0.04/0.413	0.07/0.413	5.18E+04
PE/PE/Gr/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/Gr/Gr/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/Gr/ PE/PE	0.04/0.413	0.07/0.413	4.30E+04
Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/ PE/Gr	0.04/0.413	0.07/0.413	4.24E+04
PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/GR/Gr/PE/Gr/PE/Gr/PE /GR/PE	0.04/0.413	0.07/0.413	3.88E+04